

Labor unions in Wisconsin: What You Need to Know

Labor unions have a long, proud history in the United States. Long before the term “union-buster” was even a glimmer in anyone’s eye, labor unions had started fighting for their rights and benefits. Today, labor unions make up a small but important part of the American workforce. They help workers earn a decent wage and form a union if they feel they are being mistreated by their employer. That being said, there is still plenty of room for improvement when it comes to the treatment of union members in certain industries and states. That’s why Naomi Soldon, [an attorney specialized in labor law](#), created this article on labor unions in Wisconsin so that you don’t make the same mistakes we did when looking into this topic for yourself. Keep reading to discover everything you need to know about joining a union in Wisconsin.

What is a union in Wisconsin?

According to Naomi Soldon, a labor union in Wisconsin is a group of employees who have come together under the auspices of a labor union to negotiate on behalf of their interests as workers. While a union represents the interest of all workers in a company, it can be either a bargaining unit or a monopsony union. A monopsony union is one in which only one union represents all workers in the state. You can learn more about what types of unions are present in your area by visiting the Wisconsin Labor Relations Council’s website.

How to Join a Union in Wisconsin

Naomi Soldon indicates that you can join a union in Wisconsin simply by signing up to be a member of a union. There are two types of unions: collective bargaining and certified public employee unions. Each type has its own set of rules and requirements, and you can choose which type of union you want to join.

Collective Bargaining - The collective bargaining process is the one that determines the terms and conditions under which employees can negotiate with their employers. It is the type of collective bargaining that most often occurs in unionized workplaces.

Certified Public Employee Unions - These are unions that are recognized as representing certain types of employees, including public employees and unionized professionals.

Impact of Right to Work in Wisconsin

Right to Work is a law that prevents working people in union workplaces from joining a union if they want to. [Naomi Soldon](#) indicates that the law only applies to private sector employees and those who work for government contractors. It does not apply to members of the military or employees in state-owned facilities.

Bottom line

“When it comes to labor unions in Wisconsin, make no mistake about it. They are not your enemy. They just want to help out their members and improve the working conditions for everyone,” says Naomi Soldon who has [an extensive experience in employment law](#).

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